

EDUCATOR IN RAISING THE SPIRITUALITY OF YOUNG PEOPLE ROLE AND ROLE OF PERSONNEL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11912390>

Abstract. *In this article, the place and role of pedagogues in improving the spirituality of young people, as well as information about the opportunities given to our young people and the goals and tasks of pedagogic staff are presented. Also, information about the conditions of using the foreign experiences of pedagogues was provided.*

Key words: *world, higher education, spirituality, potential, innovation, activity, knowledge, reserve*

ПЕДАГОГ В ПОДГОТОВКЕ ДУХОВНОСТИ МОЛОДЕЖИ РОЛЬ И РОЛЬ ПЕРСОНАЛА

Аннотация. *В данной статье представлены место и роль педагогов в повышении духовности молодежи, а также информация о возможностях, предоставляемых нашей молодежи, а также целях и задачах педагогических кадров. Также была предоставлена информация об условиях использования зарубежного опыта педагогов.*

Ключевые слова: *мир, высшее образование, духовность, потенциал, инновации, активность, знания, резерв.*

INTRODUCTION

In the developed higher education system in the world, as one of the directions of training specialists for professional activity, preparing future professors-teachers for innovative activities, fully manifesting their individual creative activity, developing their intellectual potential, increasing their knowledge, innovative in the process of which the problems of preparation for the implementation of activities have a special place, the accumulation of acquired knowledge reserves, skills and qualifications, the successful solution of these problems, the reconstruction of the higher pedagogical education system, the clarification of its goals and tasks, the education of the content of personnel training requires improvement in accordance with the new requirements of the innovative system in the field. Teachings related to the training of pedagogical personnel and pedagogical activities are also reflected in the works created before Christ.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In the East, the source of Zoroastrian teachings is in "Avesta" (1st century BC), the holy book of Islam "Holy Qur'an" (7th century) and "Hadith Sharif" (Imam al-Bukhari "Al-jame' as-sahih", IX century), among the Central Asian renaissance thinkers Abu Nasr al-Farabi ("The City of Virtuous People", 70-80s of the 10th century), Abu Ali Ibn Sina ("The Wisdom", XI century), Burkhaniddin Zarnudji (Ta'lim al-Mutaalallim, 12th century), Muslihiddin Sa'di Shirozi ("Boston", 1257, "Gulistan", 1258), Alisher Navoi ("Collection of perfect works" 20 volumes, 1987-2003) in artistic-philosophical works, in the teachings of great philosophers, pedagogues, thinkers such as Democritus, Socrates, Plato, Aristotle, Marcus Fabius Quintilian, Jan Amos Comenius, Adolf Distegweg in Ancient Greece and Rome in the West, in the form of educational and moral works. , expressed valuable opinions about pedagogical activity and its content.¹

When we talk about financing the quality of teacher training, we certainly think that it is impossible not to refer to the decisions and decrees of the President of our country, Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miromonovich, as well as the laws that are being adopted in our country, which are related to education. First, let's get acquainted with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. Today, the public education system has a total of 4,916 preschool educational institutions, 9,680 general secondary schools, 211 "Barkamol Avlod" centers, with a total of more than 400,000 teaching staff. is doing.

In the system of the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, there are 5 state pedagogical institutes for the training of pedagogic personnel, 14 regional institutes for the retraining of public education workers and improving their qualifications. it is an important link not only in the preparation of educated citizens and the formation of the country's human capital, but also in the preservation, development and transmission of existing teaching values to the next generation. Pedagogical training has and will always have a clear historical description.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The scholars of the East and Central Asia of the next period, spiritual and enlightened schools, said valuable words about the essence of the pedagogic profession, its socio-economic description. We see this clearly in the teachings of Abdulla Avloni, Oibek, Gafur Ghulam, Abdullah Oripov and the younger generation. Analyzing the professional component of the future pedagogue, E.A. Tekhanova reveals his ability to solve problems arising in real situations in

¹ [Druzhirov S.A. Professional competence and professionalism of the teacher: psychological approach. // Siberia. Philosophy. Education Nauchno-publitsistichesky almanac: So RAO, IPK, Novokuznetsk, 2005. -S.90.]

professional pedagogical activities using his knowledge, professional and life experience, and interests.

In the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 27, 2020 "On measures to further develop the field of pedagogical education" No. PQ-4623, further improvement of the field of pedagogical education, use of modern knowledge and pedagogical technologies It was noted that the main goal is to supply professional pedagogic personnel and introduce advanced educational technologies in the field in order to train highly qualified specialists who have learning skills and make a worthy contribution to the socio-economic development of our country. "Development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" also discusses this topic and defines a number of priority tasks.

There are no special pedagogical higher education organizations in European countries, but there are large universities that include pedagogical institutes. According to European standards, the opportunity to move between different sectors and professions within the framework of education is provided by many post-secondary education programs, which provide a sufficient level of qualification to the future teacher. Finland's teacher training system serves as a model for many countries. At the end of the last century, the master's degree was established as the minimum standard of education for teachers (including pedagogues), which to some extent made an important contribution to increasing the respect and social status of pedagogues in the country.²

In order to become school and pre-school pedagogues in Finland, it is necessary to go through a very strict selection: the best students-graduates of pedagogy specialties are employed in schools around 12%. Another positive aspect of the Finnish education system is the priority given to teaching in small groups. This undoubtedly leads to high quality of education.

In a number of countries of America, Europe and Asia, the general trend in the training of pedagogues is to increase the prestige of the pedagogic profession, to provide and retain the work of professionally qualified pedagogues, to improve the personnel policy, to attract pedagogues to work on themselves, to develop professional teams, and modern pedagogical technologies. is to direct efforts to increase professional competence through.

CONCLUSION

The next stage of reforms in the education system in Uzbekistan is the transition to the training of a narrow range of specialists-pedagogues based on advanced foreign experience. This, in turn, makes it an objective necessity to train pedagogic personnel based on the identification of specific needs in each direction. According to I.D. Frumin, it is necessary to use the successful

² [1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 23, 2020 "On Education" No. ORQ-637.]

experience of foreign countries or to look for a unique way of developing the pedagogical system of training and professional development of pedagogical personnel.

REFERENCES

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 23, 2020 "On Education" No. ORQ-637.
2. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis of January 24, 2020.
3. Resolution PQ-4623 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 27, 2020 "On measures to further develop the field of pedagogical education".
4. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026"
5. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. From national revival to national rise. -Tashkent: Uzbekistan. 2020. -B. 143.
6. Akhadjon oglu, A. A. (2024). THE POSITIVE EFFECT OF MEMBERSHIP OF THE WTO ON THE DIGITAL ECONOMY AND EDUCATION. Analysis of International Sciences, 2(1), 95-102.
7. O Makhliyo Khan. (2024). USE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN PRIMARY EDUCATION. Analysis of International Sciences 2 (1), 87-91
8. Egamberdiyev, O. A. O., Turdaliyev, A. Y. O., & Makhamadjonov, J. Z. O. (2021). Pedagogical bases of formation of professional competence. Science and Education, 2(11), 985-991.
9. Zarnigor, R. A. Q., Egamberdiyev, O. A. O. G. L., & Sotvoldiyeva, O. M. R. Q. (2021). Pedagogical competence: theoretical and practical analysis. Science and Education, 2(9), 309-314.
10. Egamberdiyev, O. A. O., Sotvoldiyeva, O. M. Q., & Turdaliyev, A. Y. O. (2021). PROBLEM WAYS OF DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 1(10), 535-542.
11. Yusufovich, A. A. (2020). ISSUES OF FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE, WHICH IS AN INTEGRAL PART OF PROFESSIONAL-PEDAGOGICAL TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol, 8(7).

12. Tojimamatov, J., & Egamberdiyev, O. (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN THE FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH OF A PERSON.
13. Egamberdiyev, O., Kholdarova, Z., & Khusanova, M. (2022). THE ORDER OF THE APPEARANCE OF THE PEOPLE'S DIPLOMACY OF THE GREAT SILK ROAD COUNTRIES.
14. Egamberdiyev, O. A., ugli Makhamadjonov, J. Z., & kizi Sobirova, A. M. (2022). NEED TO FORM CREATIVE COMPETENCE IN EDUCATORS. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 1(3), 162-165.